

Mobile Technologies applied to protect victims of a crime within the EU Area of Justice: RightsApp for e-Justice

D5.2 Conference papers

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ACRONYMS LIST:

EU: European Union

FEPSU: Spanish Forum for the Prevention and Urban Security

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document lists the conference papers resulting from the RightsApp project. The COVID-19 pandemic has caused the postponement or even cancellation of some of the main criminology and crime victims support conferences. Therefore, besides the dissemination activities in conferences already held, the RightsApp research team has included in this document the conferences which the research team is currently working on in order to send a contribution with the project's outcomes and results.

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1 CONFERENCES

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused the postponement or even cancellation of some of the main conferences, workshops face-to-face meetings. This situation rose precisely when the main outcomes and results of the project had become available and the dissemination activities could start to share these results. Consequently, the RightsApp research team has reshaped the greatest part of these dissemination activities (for instance, see RightsApp Deliverable D5.7 – “Public events” and D5.9 – “Final International Workshop”) in order to reach general public, academia and stakeholders and to accomplish all the objectives initially planned for the project. As mentioned above, conferences, workshops and, in general, all face-to-face meetings have deeply suffered the consequences of the pandemic. Therefore, besides the dissemination activities in conferences already held, the RightsApp research team has included in this document the next editions of targeted conferences which the research team is currently working to send a contribution.

Section 1.1 list the conference already held: “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” and section 1.2 consists of the conferences for which the research team is preparing a contribution.

1.1 Attended conferences

The Security and Prevention Department of the Barcelona City Council acting as Executive Delegate of the Spanish Forum for the Prevention and Urban Security (FEPSU) organized the “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” public event. As a result of the collaboration between the Security and Prevention Department and the RightsApp project, the RightsApp research members Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero and Dr. Emma Teodoro were invited to exhibit a RightsApp poster. The event was addressed to scholars, stakeholders and practitioners, and provided an excellent opportunity to disseminate the project. The details of the event are listed in RightsApp Deliverable D5.7 – “Public events”. Briefly, the event was held the 28th of March 2019 (M13) at the Pompeu Fabra University facilities (Campus de la Ciutadella). The Programme and the Conclusions documents are available online in Spanish at: <http://fepsu.es/nuevos-retos-nuevas-respuestas-innovacion-y-seguridad-urbana/>. The RightsApp Home Page has also published information about this event at: <http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/2019/03/27/rightsapp-in-new-challenges-new-answers-innovation-and-urban-security/>.

Figure 1 shows the event poster and Figure 2 depicts a screenshot of the programme where the RightsApp poster is announced (highlighted with a blue square). Although the main language used in this event was Spanish, the materials reported in this document have been translated into English when it has been possible and useful for the reader.

Figure 1: New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security

Figure 2: "New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security" programme

Figure 3: RightsApp poster for the “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” event

Figure 3 shows the poster that Dr. Jorge Gonzalez-Conejero and Dr. Emma Teodoro exhibited in the event. Table 1 reports the translation to English of the main parts of the poster for the sake of clearness. The organization informed that the approximate number of attendants to the session poster was 55 people. The event was addressed to scholars, stakeholders and practitioners, and provided an excellent opportunity to disseminate the project among public. Table 2 briefs on the event details and includes the link to the information regarding this event published in the RightsApp Home Page.

RightsApp project
The RightsApp project aims to improve the access to justice for European citizens via the use of mobile technologies and the effective implementation of their rights when they fall victims to a crime.
Why is RightsApp an innovative experience?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project endows an active role to European citizens regarding the effective implementation of their rights as crime victims. • Mobile technologies are used in order to empower the citizens and ensure their right to access to justice. • Thanks to the details provided by the user, the mobile application furnishes the victims with suitable information considering their particular situation. • The information provided by the App is understandable for the user and minimizes the use of legal technicalities. It is available in several languages (Spanish, English, Portuguese and Italian).
Main activities and results
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The access of European citizens to justice, even in cross-border situations, has been improved. • The project has contributed to ensure a wider implementation and knowledge of the European citizens’ rights via the RightsApp application.

Table 1: English translation of the most relevant parts of the RightsApp poster exhibited at “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security”

Event	New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security
Title	Projects and experiences: RightsApp project
Organizer	Spanish Forum for the Prevention and Urban Security (Forum Español para la Prevención y la Seguridad Urbana, FEPSU)
Information published at the RightsApp Home Page	http://rightsapp-project.uab.cat/index.php/2019/03/27/rightsapp-in-new-challenges-new-answers-innovation-and-urban-security/
Date	28 th March 2019
Project month	M13
Place	Universidad Pompeu Fabra, Campus de la Ciutadella, Barcelona, Spain
Responsible	Dr. Jorge González-Conejero and Dr. Emma Teodoro
Audience	Academia, stakeholders and practitioners
Number of attendants	55 people

Language of the event	Although some of the tools and initiatives exhibited in the event were developed in English, the main language used in the event was Spanish
Language of the materials	Spanish (translated to English for the deliverable)

Table 2: “New challenges, new answers: innovation and urban security” event details

It is worth noticing that Prof. Pompeu Casanovas was going to attend and make a presentation at the Shonan Meeting n. 172 at NII, Japan, from March 1st to 5th. He was already registered, but *Policy Modelling and Reasoning*, organised by Marina De Vos (University of Bath, UK), Sabrina Kirrane (University of Economics and Business, Austria), Julian Padget (University of Bath, UK) and Ken Satoh (National Institute of Informatics, Japan) was cancelled at the last moment.

1.2 Upcoming conferences

The COVID-19 pandemic has reshaped all face-to-face activities in Europe for the past months. Obviously, conferences and workshops have also been affected across Europe. In general terms, face-to-face meetings across Europe are strongly discouraged.

The two main conferences in the agenda of the RightsApp research team are:

- 20th Annual Conference of the European Society of Criminology¹
- JURIX 2020/2021² (upcoming AICOL-Workshop)

The 20th Annual Conference of the European Society of Criminology has been postponed. It is expected to be held in September 2021 in Bucharest (Romania). From a criminological point of view, this is the most relevant international conference. This conference is hosted by the European Society of Criminology and allows scholars to present papers on the results of research projects as well as to learn about the research carried out elsewhere in Europe. Therefore, the RightsApp research team is committed to introduce a paper in the upcoming Annual Conference of the European Society of Criminology. The 2020 edition of the JURIX³ conference will be virtually held. The conference is annually organised by JURIX, an association of researchers in the field of Law and Computer Science. Since 1988, JURIX⁴ has held annual international conferences on Legal Knowledge and Information Systems. The JURIX meetings have already proved to be an important platform for new pan-European research initiatives. However, and due the last extension of the project caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the end date for the RightsApp project almost coincides with the deadline for papers submission (21st September 2020). Against this background, the RightsApp research team has decided to take the following actions: (i) to postpone the submission of the paper until next year’s edition and, (ii) to focus on the 20th Annual Conference of the European Society of Criminology whose deadline is 15th April 2021. However, the new edition of the *International Workshop on AI Approaches to the Complexity of Legal Systems@Jurix2020* gives us the opportunity to submit a paper to be published at the AICOL Series (LNAI).⁵

¹ <https://www.eurocrim2021.com/>

² <https://jurix2020.law.muni.cz/>

³ <https://jurix2020.law.muni.cz/>

⁴ <http://jurix.nl/>

⁵ <http://www.aicol.eu/> <https://www.springer.com/gp/book/9783030001773>